

Connect with

Social Sciences & Humanities
for Climate, Energy and
Transport Research Excellence

sshcentre.eu

Society faces significant and increasing climate, energy and mobility challenges, which require innovative action to address.

SSH CENTRE
is the new cross-Europe
centre of excellence for
Climate-Energy-Mobility
Social Sciences &
Humanities (SSH)
research, running from
2022 to 2026.

The Social Sciences & Humanities for Climate, Energy and Transport Research Excellence (SSH CENTRE) project is a [Euro-sign]3m project running over 2022-2026 and coordinated by 13 leading organisations from across Europe:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101069529 and from UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee [grant No 10038991].

Take part in our collaborative, funded activities:

Training programme for researchers on bridging between
research and policy

Small grants for new collaborations between transition-focused
SSH* and STEM**

Virtual SSH CENTRE Open Knowledge Platform,
connecting over 600 members to strengthen Climate-Energy-Mobility SSH research across Europe

Regular Policy Insight events with senior representatives from
EC/European Parliament, civil society, academia, and the private sector

Stay in touch

Keep up to date with our funded activities to support a cross-sectoral and socially innovative climate transition.

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*Social Sciences and Humanities

**Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics